

Evaluation of Surface Water Quality for Irrigation use in Dukku Fadama, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State

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Abstract

Water is one of the most essential resources for sustaining life on Earth, playing a vital role in human survival, socioeconomic development, and the maintenance of ecosystems. This experiment was conducted during 2024 dry season with the aim of assessing the quality of surface water for irrigation along Dukku River in Kebbi State. Water samples were taken from the sampling point of the River designated as (P1, P2 and P3). From each sampling point, five samples of water were collected in clean PVC bottles. Each water sample was analyzed for pH, Electrical Conductivity (Ec), Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR), Calcium (Ca), Magnesium (Mg), Potassium (K), Sodium (Na), Chloride (Cl⁻) Ion (Fe), Boron (Br), Carbonate (CO₃²⁻) and Bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) using standard procedures in the Soil Science Laboratory of Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology Aliero for about Two (2) weeks. Results obtained showed ranges and the overall means of pH, EC, Mg, Na, K, Ca, Fe, Bo, Cl, CO₃, HCO₃, SAR, for each location to be 6.72-7.22 (7.01), 2.44-3.01(2.66)mg/l, 0.12-0.19 (0.15)mg/l, 0.01(0.01)mg/l, 1.65-1.95(1.78)mg/l, 0.30-0.32(0.31)mg/l, 0.01-0.04 (0.02)mg/l, 0.03 (0.03)mg/l, 14.04-14.08 (14.06)mg/l, 27.06-27.09 (27.07)mg/l and 0.20-0.29 (0.24)mg/l, respectively. Furthermore, results obtained revealed that all the parameters analyzed were within the permissible limit of irrigation of most of agricultural crops under good management and therefore could be considered Safe for irrigation activities.

Keywords: Assessment, Dukku, Fadama, Quality, Surface and Water.

1.0 Introduction

Water is one of the most essential resources for sustaining life on Earth, playing a vital role in human survival, socioeconomic development, and the maintenance of ecosystems.^[1] In agriculture, water is particularly critical as irrigation directly influences all stages of crop production, from seedbed preparation, germination, root establishment, nutrient uptake, plant growth, and regrowth, to yield and quality of produce. Irrigation is also indispensable in making soils productive in areas where rainfall or natural flooding is insufficient.^[2] However, while much attention has often been placed on the availability of water for irrigation, the issue of water quality has frequently been neglected, despite its importance in

determining soil health, crop performance, and the overall sustainability of irrigated agriculture.^[3] Water used for irrigation commonly contains dissolved salts and other chemical constituents, which, depending on their concentration and composition, may either enhance or hinder plant growth. Poor-quality water can cause problems such as salinity, toxicity, reduced infiltration, nutrient imbalance, and even contamination by heavy metals, nitrates, and pathogens.^[4]

In Nigeria, the effect of water quality on agricultural productivity is evident, with the national average rice yield estimated at 3 tons per hectare, far below the international average of 6 tons per hectare.^[5] This low productivity may be partly attributed to the use of irrigation water of

poor quality, among other limiting factors.^[5] In the Dukku Fadama Land of Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, water resources are increasingly threatened by agricultural runoff carrying pesticides and fertilizers, industrial discharges introducing heavy metals and other pollutants, and domestic waste leading to organic and microbial contamination. The lack of regular water quality monitoring in the area compounds these risks, as potential contaminants often go undetected.^[5]

Given the importance of water quality for sustainable irrigated agriculture, there is a clear need to assess the quality of irrigation water in Dukku Fadama Land. Such an assessment is justified by its potential to prevent soil degradation, minimize salinity and sodicity problems, and improve crop yields under proper management practices. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to evaluate the quality of irrigation water in Dukku Fadama Land, Birnin Kebbi, with a view to determining its suitability for crop production and ensuring long-term agricultural sustainability in the area.

Figure 1: Map of Kebbi State showing Dukku River

2.2 Sample collection

Water samples from the River were taken during the dry seasons of 2024. Water samples were collected in three different points namely; the upper, middle and lower positions of the River. Thus giving a total of three (3) collection points designated as follow; P1, P2 and P3 Respectively.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Study Area

The study was conducted at Dukku River, Birnin Kebbi. Dukku River is a major river supplying water to Kebbi State Water Board, Birnin Kebbi. The river is also used as a source of water for irrigation around the area. Birnin Kebbi lies at latitude $12^{\circ} 27'57''N$ and longitude $4^{\circ} 11'58''E$ and an altitude of 225m above the sea level in the Sudan Savannah vegetation zone in northern Nigeria. The soil in the area is very susceptible to erosion due to their coarse texture, poor soil structure as result low organic matter and low clay contents. The area has a semi arid climate that is characterized by a long dry season (October-May) and a short wet season (June-September) with a mean annual rainfall of 665mm. The temperature ranges between $22^{\circ}C$ to $45^{\circ}C$.

Where 'P' stands for River water samples. While 1, 2, and 3 represent upper, middle and lower positions of the dam respectively. A total of five (5) samples was obtained from each sampling unit, given a total of 15 Samples. The water samples from the River were collected below the water surface using PVC bottles which were transported to the laboratory for the immediate analysis of chemical properties, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solid, sodium, potassium, chlorine, borone, calcium, magnesium, iron, manganese, bicarbonate, water temperature and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR).

2.3 Analytical Procedure

The pH of was measured electrometrically using glass electrode pH meter.^[6] Electrical conductivity was measured with electrical conductivity meter. Sodium, potassium, chlorine and boron were determined using flame photometer, while calcium, magnesium, iron and manganese were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS).^[6] Bicarbonate was determined by the titrimetric method using naphthalene or methyl orange as indicator.^[6] Total dissolved solids in water was determined by evaporation-drying^[6]. The temperature of the water samples was measured by thermometer (mercury-in-glass). Sodium

Adsorption Ratio (SAR) was calculated using the formula below.

$$\text{SAR} = \frac{\text{Na}^{2+}}{\frac{\sqrt{\text{Ca} + \text{Mg}}}{2}}$$

Residual Sodium Carbonate (RSC) was calculated using the formula below as recommended by (Doneen, 1964).

$$\text{RSC} = (\text{CO}_3 + \text{HCO}_3) - (\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+})$$

2.4 Statistical Analysis

The Data obtained were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) $p = 0.05$ using SAS software. Significance differences among means were separated using Least Significance Difference (LSD).

3.0 Results

Table 1 showed that the pH of the water in the study area across the three samples ranged from 6.72 to 7.22. This indicated that the water samples varied from slightly acidic to neutral, with P2 and P3 falling within the ideal range for most biological and agricultural uses.

Electrical conductivity (EC) values were recorded as 2.44 ds/m, 2.55 ds/m, and 3.01 ds/m. These values reflect the concentration of dissolved salts in the water, with higher EC indicating increased salinity. The concentrations of magnesium (Mg^{2+}) were found to be 0.12 mg/l, 0.15 mg/l, and 0.19 mg/l. These values suggest that magnesium content in the water is relatively low and unlikely to contribute significantly to hardness or soil degradation.

Sodium (Na^+) levels remained consistent at 0.01 mg/l across all three samples, indicating minimal sodium accumulation, which is beneficial for irrigation. Potassium (K^+) levels ranged between 0.03 to 0.04 mg/l, confirming that potassium concentrations were low but sufficient for natural water systems without contributing to any adverse effects.

The calcium (Ca^{2+}) concentrations were measured at 0.32 mg/l in P1, 0.30 mg/l in P2, and 0.31 mg/l in P3. These values indicate that the water is soft to moderately hard, with no significant impact on scale formation in pipes or interference with soap lathering.

Iron (Fe) levels varied slightly, with P3 showing a slightly higher concentration at 0.02 mg/l, while P1 and P2 remained at 0.01 mg/l. These values suggest that the iron content is within permissible limits and is unlikely to cause staining or affect water taste.

Boron (Bo) levels were found to be 0.03 mg/l in P1 and P3, while P2 had a slightly higher concentration of 0.04 mg/l. Given that boron is an essential micronutrient for plant growth but can be toxic at high concentrations, the values obtained indicate that the water remains safe for irrigation without posing risks of boron toxicity.

Chloride (Cl^-) levels remained relatively stable, with P1 and P3 containing 0.13 mg/l and P2 showing a slightly lower value of 0.10 mg/l. These values suggest that the water is not significantly saline and is suitable for most uses.

Manganese recorded the values of 14.08 mg/l in P1, 14.04 mg/l in P2, and 14.06 mg/l in P3, these values are significantly higher than the World Health Organization's recommended limit of 0.1 mg/l for drinking water, indicating the potential need for treatment before human consumption.

Carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) and bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) levels were found to be relatively high across all samples, with values of 27.09 mg/l in P1, 27.06 mg/l in P2, and 27.07 mg/l in P3. These elevated bicarbonate concentrations suggest a moderate level of alkalinity, which may affect soil quality over time if used for irrigation. High bicarbonate levels can lead to increased soil pH, which in turn affects nutrient availability

The SAR values are lesser than 10 meq/l for the samples taken, therefore it is graded as excellent for irrigation use (Table 1). SAR is a measure of tendency of sodium (Na) ion to displace Ca ion in the irrigation water soil.

Table 4.1: Mean Water Quality Concentration of Irrigation Water of Dukku River During 2024 dry season

Samples	Ph	EC ds/m	Mg mg/l	Na mg/l	K mg/l	Ca mg/l	Fe mg/l	Bo mg/l	Cl mg/l	CO ₃ ⁻ mg/l	HCO ₃ ⁻ mg/l	SAR mg/l
P1	6.72	2.44	0.12	0.01	1.95	0.01	0.32	0.04	0.03	14.08	27.09	0.29
P2	7.10	2.55	0.15	0.01	1.72	0.01	0.30	0.01	0.03	14.04	27.06	0.25
P3	7.22	3.01	0.19	0.01	1.65	0.01	0.31	0.02	0.03	14.06	27.07	0.20
Overall Means	7.01	2.66	0.15	0.01	1.78	0.01	0.31	0.02	0.03	14.06	27.07	0.24
S.E	0.37	0.92	0.24	0.12	0.72	0.21	0.77	0.35	0.41	0.51	0.98	0.42
Significance	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

4.0 Discussion

A comparison of the mean pH values obtained (Table 1) with the recommended irrigation water range of 6.0–8.4 showed that all samples were within acceptable limits. This indicated that the river water was not alkaline and thus suitable for irrigation. Irrigation water with pH values outside this range could lead to nutrient imbalances or toxic ion accumulation in the soil.^[7] Similar observations were reported by^[8] who found that pH values of surface waters used for irrigation generally fell within safe ranges, suggesting minimal risk of alkalinity-related soil problems.

The maximum permissible limit for electrical conductivity (EC) in irrigation water is 3 dS/m. The EC values in this study ranged from moderate to extreme, suggesting potential restrictions for irrigation use. Elevated EC values reflected higher concentrations of dissolved salts and organic matter. Comparable findings were reported by^[9], where EC values also indicated potential salinity hazards for long-term irrigation. However, the EC values observed in this study were higher than those reported by^[10], highlighting spatial variability in water quality across Nigerian river systems.

The relatively low and stable concentrations of calcium (Ca²⁺) and magnesium (Mg²⁺) across sampling points suggested suitability of the water for irrigation. None of the samples exceeded the recommended thresholds, indicating no associated risks. This finding agrees with^[7] who similarly reported low Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ levels in river water used for irrigation. Excessive levels of these cations could otherwise increase soil pH and reduce phosphorus availability to crops.

Sodium (Na⁺) concentrations in the river water samples remained well below the maximum threshold of 100 mg/L (Table 1), indicating low sodium hazard and confirming suitability for irrigation. This result aligns with the work of^[11], who also found low sodium concentrations in irrigation water, while contrasting with results from^[12], where higher sodium levels were reported in arid regions due to increased evaporation and salt accumulation.

Potassium (K⁺) concentrations in many samples approached the threshold of 2 mg/L. Inorganic fertilizers commonly used in the study area often contain nitrogen, phosphorus, or potassium. Since only a fraction of applied nutrients is absorbed by crops, residual portions can accumulate in the soil and leach into nearby water bodies. Potassium might also have originated from natural rock weathering. Similar sources of potassium were identified by^[13] Given the relatively low nitrogen concentrations in the present study, potassium was more likely derived from rock dissolution rather than anthropogenic inputs.

Boron (B), an essential micronutrient required for cell wall formation and plant metabolism, was detected at concentrations ranging from 0.01 to 0.04 mg/L. These levels were low but require continuous monitoring to ensure safe irrigation use. Comparable concentrations were reported by^[14], who noted that boron levels in irrigation water in Malaysia were generally below the toxicity threshold for crops.

Chloride (Cl⁻), which can become toxic at elevated levels, remained within the safe concentration range recommended for irrigation water (Table 1). This finding is in line with the results of^[15], who also observed chloride concentrations within acceptable

limits in irrigation water from southwestern Nigeria.

Similarly, carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) and bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) concentrations during the dry season were stable and below the maximum permissible limit of 500 mg/L. These results agree with ^[16], who reported that bicarbonates were generally predominant over carbonates in Nigerian river systems at near-neutral pH values. Significant carbonate presence typically occurs only at pH values above 9.0, which was not the case in this study.

The Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR) was also evaluated as a key parameter in irrigation water assessment, since excessive sodium can degrade soil structure and reduce permeability. The SAR values obtained in this study fell within the “excellent” category, confirming that the river water posed no sodium hazard and was safe for irrigation (Table 1). These results are consistent with the findings of ^[17], who also reported SAR values within the excellent range for irrigation use in Nigerian river waters

5.0 Conclusion

This study assessed the Surface water quality across three sampling points (P1, P2, and P3) to determine its suitability for irrigation activities. The results revealed that the water quality in the study area is generally suitable for irrigation, with no significant restrictions observed for most agricultural crops. However, care should be taken in monitoring Potassium levels so as to avoid its further concentration to the toxic level. Management strategies must also be applied to prevent long term effects of Alkalinity on the soils of the study area.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the results obtained, the following recommendations would be given: -

1. As a result of low concentration of Ca, Na, Mg, Cl, Fe, Bo and SAR ions in the water of the study area, farmers could be advised to ensure light but frequent irrigation with this water for most of the agricultural crops.
2. Moderate concentration of CO_3^{2-} and HCO_3^- revealed in this study, farmers would be

advised to apply proper irrigation management practices to prevent the soil from being saline or sodic which might have detrimental effects on growing crops and soil physical characteristics.

3. Based on the salinity and sodicity parameters such as pH and Ec, the water could be used for irrigation without any restrictions.

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

This work is a collaboration of all the authors. All Authors read and approved the final manuscript. They declare that they have no competing interests.

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